

Supplement 4: qPCR results

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Figure 1-S4 Determining the LOD by means of artificial contamination.

The figure shows the Cq values of *mecA* amplification in BM artificially contaminated with MRSA 28766. The LOD of *mecA* was tested with primer No. 4 and a cut-off value of 32 using a dilution series of MRSA added to pooled bulk milk (cells \times mL⁻¹ milk). 0a-b = 2.618×10^4 ; 1a-c = 1.047×10^4 ; 2a-c = 5.235×10^3 ; 3a-c = 2.618×10^3 ; 4a-c = 1.309×10^3 ; 5a-c = 6.545×10^2 ; 6a-c = 3.273×10^2 ; 7a-b = 1.63×10^2 ; NTC = Non-template control. Line = cutoff at mean Cq = 32.

Figure 2-S4 Melting curves of *mecA* in BMS artificially contaminated with MRSA 28766

The figure shows the melting curves of the *mecA* amplificates (using primer No. 4) in bulk milk artificially contaminated with MRSA 28766. Two main melting points are evident: between 79.5 and 80.5°C, and between 82 and 83°C. Milk samples with higher MRSA concentrations (samples 0 to 4; blue and gray lines) have their melting point between 79.5 and 80.5°C, while milk samples with lower MRSA concentrations exhibit a higher melting point (between 82 and 83°C), which might indicate non-specific amplification.

Figure 3-S4 Typical melting curves generated in the artificial contamination assay

A = typical melting curve of *mecA*; B = *mecA* > unspecific amplicon; C = *mecA* < unspecific amplicon; D = primer amplicon < second unspecific product; E = melting curve of 1 or of 3 non-template-controls, likely due to self-complementarity of primers (hairpin formation)

Figure 4-S4 Melting curves of the *mecA*-amplicon in two different BMS

The melting curve of the *mecA*-amplicon in BMS 111 resembled to the *mecA*-control, but with a slight shift, which might be indicative of point mutations. BMS 52 presents unspecific amplicons only. *mecA* + = *mecA* control; NTC = Non-template control